

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE AND ONE HEALTH

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) occurs when bacteria, viruses, fungi and parasites change over time and no longer respond to drugs, make infections difficult to treat and increase the risk of disease spread results into severe illness and death. As a result of drug resistance, antibiotics and other antimicrobial drugs become ineffective. In 2019, approximately 297,000 deaths were directly attributed to AMR in India, with another 1,042,500 deaths associated with AMR as a contributing factor. This makes India a significant contributor to the global AMR crisis, which is considered to be driven by high antibiotic consumption and misuse.

The top five pathogens associated with AMR deaths were *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

High population density, inadequate sanitation, and the overuse and misuse of antibiotics in humans and animals are major drivers of AMR in India. According to WHO, AMR could claim up to 10 million lives per year globally by 2050, over-taking cancer as the leading cause of death worldwide with India expected to see around 2 million deaths attributable to AMR by that year.

The World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH) has cautioned that uncontrolled resistance could make infections in humans, animals and plants untreatable, destabilizing food security and global health. Overuse and misuse of antibiotics in human medicine, livestock, and agriculture are accelerating this resistance. "Whenever antibiotics are used unnecessarily or stopped midway, or when they are added to animal feed for faster growth, resistant microbes become stronger," "If this continues, even a simple infection could turn life threatening."

One Health approach recognizes the inter-connection between human, animal, and environmental health. Nearly 60 percent of human infections originate from animals, hence, collaborative action across medical, veterinary and

environmental sectors is essential. "AMR is not only a medical issue but a multi sectoral challenge. Only a One Health approach can safeguard our collective future.

Widespread use of antibiotics for growth promotion or prevention of disease in livestock is a significant factor. The group treatment in food animals is long-term, low-dose mass medication for purposes of growth promotion. Antimicrobial growth promoters are important contributors to antimicrobial resistance because they are administered to entire groups of animals, usually for prolonged periods of time and often at sub therapeutic doses favour the spread of resistant bacteria within and between groups of animals, as well as to humans through food or other environmental pathways.

Poor hygiene and infection control practices in healthcare and community settings facilitate the spread of resistant bacteria. Infections caused by drug-resistant bacteria are difficult to treat, leading to higher death rates. Treating resistant infections is often more expensive due to the need for longer hospital stays and more complex treatments.

India faces a severe antimicrobial resistance (AMR) crisis, with millions of deaths attributed to it annually. Key drivers include widespread antibiotic overuse, self-medication, poor sanitation, and a lack of awareness.

India has taken notable steps through its National Action Plan on AMR, focusing on awareness, surveillance, and responsible antibiotic use. States like Kerala, Delhi and Madhya Pradesh have implemented strategic action plans, while school curricula in several regions now include AMR awareness. The NCERT has incorporated antibiotic resistance under the Class 12 Biology syllabus, indicating growing recognition of importance of early education. "Educating children on AMR can foster responsible habits within families and communities," Kerala and Gujarat are the first states to ban over the counter sales of antibiotics. Some antimicrobials and pesticides have also been banned for use in crops.

The World AMR Awareness Week (WAAW) is a global campaign to raise awareness and increase understanding of AMR and to promote global action to tackle the emergence and spread of drug-resistant pathogens. As one of WHO's official health campaigns, WAAW is mandated by the World Health Assembly and is commemorated annually from 18 to 24 November.

One of the key objectives of the plan is to improve awareness and understanding of AMR through effective communication, education and training. The **theme** for WAAW 2025 is “**Act Now: Protect Our Present, Secure Our Future.**” This theme underscores the urgent need to take bold, united action to address AMR. AMR is already harming our health, food systems, environment and economies. It's not a future challenge. It is happening now. Drug-resistant infections are increasing, yet awareness, investment and action are still falling short.

Building on the momentum of the 2024 United Nations General Assembly High-level Meeting on AMR, this call to action urges all stakeholders, including governments, civil society, health-care providers, veterinarians, farmers, environmental actors and the public to translate the political commitments into tangible, accountable, life-saving interventions. To “protect our present and secure our future”, we must prioritize long-term investment and strategic action in the human, animal and environmental health sectors. Strengthening surveillance, ensuring equitable access to quality medicines and diagnostics, fostering innovation and building resilient systems all require long-term investment in AMR action is a smart move for a safer, healthier future.

On the first day of the WHO's WAAW(18-24 Nov) 2025, Union Minister of Health and Family Welfare, Shri J. P.Nadda,

launched the second version of the National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance (2025–29). He emphasized that antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major public health concern that can only be addressed through collective action. He noted that the journey began in 2010 with initial discussions, followed by the launch of the first NAP-AMR in 2017. In April 2017 the National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance (NAP-AMR) developed in alignment with Global Action Plan (GAP) was launched which was to be implemented over next 5 years (2017-2021).

While AMR is a multisectoral issue and requires a One Health Approach for its containment, only when each sector, i.e., human, animal, agriculture and environment sector are committed for action to contain AMR, can the One Health approach be successful. Key strategies of AMR containment to be implemented under NAP-AMR 2.0 include strengthening awareness, education and training, enhancing laboratory capacity and infection control in healthcare facilities.

CONCLUSIONS

AMR is the one that most clearly illustrates the One Health approach. AMR is a critical global problem affecting humans, the environment, and animals. This is related to each of these three components due to the irresponsible and excessive use of antimicrobials in various sectors (agriculture, livestock, and human medicine). The challenge for One Health is to ensure that antimicrobials used in both animal and human sectors are used for therapy and never for growth promotion.

Strengthening awareness, education and training, enhancing laboratory capacity and infection control in healthcare facilities are the Key strategies of AMR containment.

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- Antimicrobial resistance: One Health approach Maria Elena Velazquez-Meza, Miguel Galarde-López, Berta Carrillo-Quiróz, Celia Mercedes Alpuche -Aranda: *Veterinary World* 2022 Mar 28;15(3):743–749. doi: [10.14202/vetworld.2022.743-749](https://doi.org/10.14202/vetworld.2022.743-749)